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Technical note on impact assessment of the AWS constellation using already operating microwave sounders

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1. Introduction

The EPS-Sterna programme will build a constellation of small satellites that each carry a microwave sounder similar to the one included in the Arctic Weather Satellite (AWS) demonstrator mission. The AWS microwave sounder will provide passive measurements of electromagnetic radiation in a broadly similar fashion as the currently operating microwave sounders in low Earth orbits do today. Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) centres have long experience from assimilating microwave sounder radiance data from spectral channels at 54 and 183 GHz regions to extract information relevant in analysis of atmospheric temperature and humidity, respectively. The use of the sounding channels is supported by the use of microwave window regions at 89 and 165 GHz to help distinguish between clear and cloud-affected data; the present-day limited-area NWP systems typically only assimilate data at cloud-free conditions. The AWS sounder will provide data at several channels spanning across all the above-mentioned microwave frequencies. The AWS sounder also includes additional channels at the 325 GHz (“sub-millimeter”) spectral region that has not been previously exploited in NWP applications.

This report is compiled as part of the research project “Performance evaluation of Arctic Weather Satellite Data” funded by the European Space Agency (ESA). One of the goals in the project is to evaluate the expected impact of the EPS-Sterna satellite constellation in NWP applications at high Northern latitudes. In this context, such NWP applications include limited-area (regional) forecast models operated by national meteorological offices of the Nordic countries. The impact evaluation will be conducted via two complementary approaches. Firstly, the expected impact is estimated based on the impacts that the currently operational microwave sounders provide. Secondly, the impact expectation will be reconsidered after sufficient amounts of real AWS satellite measurement data have been collected from the orbit. This report documents the first part of the evaluation, that is the part conducted prior to the launch of the AWS demonstrator mission.

The evaluation methodology to be applied was the subject in the earlier project deliverable D4 (“Technical note on impact assessment methodology”; August 2023). As much as relevant from the viewpoint of the present document, the methodology is briefly summarised in Section 2 below. The results from the conducted data assimilation experiments in the MetCoOp (Müller et al., 2017) and AROME-Arctic (Randriamampianina et al., 2019) operational NWP domains are presented and discussed in Sections 3 and 4, respectively. The significance and implications of the results are discussed in Section 5. Conclusions are provided in Section 6.

2. The setup of the data assimilation experiments

2.1 The initial experiments

The constellation impact assessment consists initially of two *data assimilation experiments* conducted separately in the MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic operational forecast domains shown in Figure 1. The horizontal grid resolution in both domains is 2.5 km and there are 65 vertical model levels that extend from the 12 metre height above the surface up to the 10 hPa pressure level (approximately 30 km altitude) in the stratosphere. Each experiment includes five *model runs*. All runs are in the deterministic mode so that there are no artificial perturbations (such as those introduced in ensemble prediction systems). The general setup is made as similar as possible to the operational settings as they were in 2023. There is one notable exception to this: the analysis of upper-air variables is conducted using the four-dimensional variational data assimilation (4D-Var; Courtier et al., 1994; Gustafsson et al., 2012) algorithm instead of the currently operational three-dimensional (3D-Var) algorithm. This deviation from the operational setup is justified by (i) the 4D-Var's better ability to account for actual observation times inside the data assimilation time window and (ii) the expectation that the operational systems will be upgraded to 4D-Var in a few years' time. Consistently with the operational runs, the model runs make use of the Cy43 reference code base of the HARMONIE-AROME NWP system (Bengtsson et al., 2017). The limited-area forecasts are forced at lateral boundaries by global meteorological fields provided by the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

Figure 1: The model domains at MetCoOp (purple) and AROME-Arctic (red) at the time of the study.

The model runs apply three-hourly cycling implying that each analysis uses the three-hour forecast from the previous assimilation cycle as a background field (i.e., first guess). At analysis times 00, 06, 12, and 18 UTC, the numerical forecast is integrated out to the 36-hour lead time. At the intermediate analysis times (03, 09, 15, and 21 UTC), the forecast integration is only out to the three-hour lead time to reduce the computational burden.

The arrangement of the five model runs per domain is illustrated in Table 1. The key features of the experiment setup are as follows:

- There are the one-satellite baseline runs “mc11” and “aa11” that serve as control runs. In these runs, the observation use is otherwise as in the MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic operations, but microwave sounder radiance data are assimilated from only one satellite instrument, that is MWHS-2 on the FengYun-3D satellite.
- The impact of adding satellite data in the “single-orbit” scenario is evaluated from model runs “mc21”, “aa21”, “mc31”, and “aa31”. In these runs, the observing system is enhanced by bringing additional satellites into the same orbital plane that is already covered by FengYun-3D in the one-satellite baseline runs. The two-satellite runs “mc21” and “aa21” bring in the additional data from NOAA-20. The three-satellite runs “mc31” and “aa31” bring in the additional data from both NOAA-20 and NPP satellites.
- The impact of adding satellite data in the “complementary-orbits” scenario is evaluated from model runs “mc22”, “aa22”, “mc33”, and “aa33”. In these runs, the observing system is enhanced by bringing additional satellites into orbital planes that are complementary to each other. The two-satellite runs “mc22” and “aa22” bring in the additional data from Metop-B. The three-satellite runs “mc33” and “aa33” bring in the additional data from both Metop-B and NOAA-19 satellites.

Except for FengYun-3D, the assimilated microwave sounder data includes both temperature- and humidity-sounding channels of either ATMS or the combination of AMSU-A and MHS. In all cases, the radiance data is assimilated in the form of brightness temperature and the measurement data is subjected to the variational bias correction (VarBC) algorithm (Auligne et al., 2007; Benacek and Mile, 2019).

Table 1: Arrangement of satellites and the microwave sounders in the model runs. The colour shading indicates the use of the three orbital planes.

	mc11, aa11	mc21, aa21	mc31, aa31	mc22, aa22	mc33, aa33
1. satellite	FengYun-3D ¹				
2. satellite	n/a	NOAA-20 ²	NOAA-20 ²	Metop-B ³	Metop-B ³
3. satellite	n/a	n/a	NPP ²	n/a	NOAA-19 ³

¹) MWHS-2

²) ATMS

³) AMSU-A and MHS

The experiment in the AROME-Arctic domain spans from 15th June to 9th August 2020 thus focussing on a boreal summer season. The impact evaluation covers six weeks from 29th June onwards; the first two weeks of the model runs are excluded from the evaluation. Synoptic conditions during the evaluation period inside the domain were variable. The period from 7th to 12th July was characterised by baroclinic activity with several low pressure systems that passed through the domain. This was followed by a high-pressure-dominated period from 13th to 17th July. Outside of these dates, relatively weak high and low pressure systems alternated. No wind direction dominated over the others.

In the MetCoOp domain, the focus is in a boreal winter season and the experiment spans from 14th December 2020 to 7th February 2021. Again, the impact evaluation is limited to the last six weeks of the period, that is, from 28th December onwards. Also during this six-week evaluation period, synoptic conditions were highly variable and no dominating weather patterns persisted for more than only a few days at a time. The atmospheric flow inside the MetCoOp domain was more often from the South and Southeast than from other directions, but there was a short period of relatively strong northeastern flow too.

2.2 The additional experiments

Two additional experiments are set up to cover time periods at opposite seasons as compared with the initial set of experiments. The additional experiments each consist of two model runs as follows:

- The additional AROME-Arctic experiment includes running “aa11” and “aa33” over the four-week winter period 14th December 2020 – 10th January 2021. The impact is evaluated over the last two weeks of the time period. Passages of moderate low pressure systems across the domain characterised the weather particularly in the latter half of the period.
- The additional MetCoOp experiment includes running “mc11” and “mc33” over the four-week summer period 15th June – 12th July 2020. Again, the impact evaluation is over the last two weeks of the time period. For most of the period, there was only little baroclinic activity in the domain, but in the last few days several low pressure systems passed on the Northern side of the domain.

The purpose of the additional experiments is to provide an opportunity to strengthen conclusions from the impact evaluation. This way it will be possible to consider the significance of running in different seasons on the one hand and of having slight differences in the operational setups at MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic on the other.

3. Results in the MetCoOp operational domain

3.1 Scorecard-based overall impression of the impact at winter

Figure 2 illustrates the forecast impact of the additional satellites in the single-orbit scenario of the MetCoOp winter experiment. The presentation is in the form of a scorecard that compares the MetCoOp three-satellite run “mc31” against the one-satellite baseline run “mc11”. That is, the impact shown is the accumulation of the contributions from the microwave sounders on both NOAA-20 and NPP. Each row presents the forecast impact on a specific meteorological variable; the abbreviations used are defined in Table 2. The x-axis shows the forecast lead time in increments of three and six hours for variables observed at surface and radiosonde stations, respectively. Blue triangles indicate a positive impact from the additional satellite data: that is, the root-mean-squared error (RMSE) in the forecast is smaller in “mc31” than in “mc11”. Red triangles indicate a negative impact. Statistically significant results (at 95% confidence level) are shown by large triangles. The small triangles indicate results significant at 68% confidence level. In this study, such results are considered insignificant. Where no triangle is shown, the impact is neutral.

The strongest signal in Figure 2 appears in the verification against surface-based observations of temperature, humidity, and cloud. The temperature (T2m) and humidity-related variables (Td2m, Q2m, and RH2m) consistently indicate a statistically significant positive impact throughout the forecast range from 0 to at least 30 hours. In cloud-related variables, that is, the cloud base height (Cbase) and the total cloud cover (CCtot), the solid and statistically significant impact extends from 0 to 24 hours. Also in the mean sea level pressure (Pmsl), there is a statistically significant positive impact that extends from 0 to 21 hours’ lead time. There are no such strong signals in the verification against precipitation accumulations (AccPcp3h, AccPcp6h, AccPcp12h) or near-surface wind direction (D10m) and speed (S10m). On balance, these variables indicate a slightly negative impact, but that’s rarely statistically significant at 95% confidence level.

Figure 2 shows no consistent signals in the verification of upper-air variables against radiosonde data. On balance, the upper-air verification shows a slightly negative picture with individual scores being on the negative side in more cases than on the positive side. In most cases the upper-air scores are insignificant.

Figure 2: Scorecard representation of the verification scores in the MetCoOp winter experiment for the three-satellite run in the single-orbit scenario. Blue (red) triangles indicate a statistically significant positive (negative) impact from the additional satellite data. The verification metric is root-mean-squared error (RMSE) computed against observations taken at synoptic surface and radiosonde stations.

Table 2: The meteorological variables presented in the scorecards.

Acronym	Explanation
AccPcp3h	Precipitation accumulation over three hours
AccPcp6h	Precipitation accumulation over six hours
AccPcp12h	Precipitation accumulation over twelve hours
Cbase	Cloud base height
CCtot	Total cloud cover (octas)
D10m	Wind direction at ten metres height
Pmsl	Pressure at mean sea level
T2m	Temperature at two metres height
Td2m	Dew point temperature at two metres height
Q2m	Specific humidity at two metres height
RH2m	Relative humidity at two metres height
S10m	Wind speed at 10 metres height
Z300, Z500, Z850	Geopotential height at 300, 500, and 850 hPa levels
T300, T500, T850	Temperature at 300, 500, and 850 hPa levels
RH300, RH500, RH850	Relative humidity at 300, 500, and 850 hPa levels
Q300, Q500, Q850	Specific humidity at 300, 500, and 850 hPa levels
S300, S500, S850	Wind speed at 300, 500, and 850 hPa levels

Figure 3 shows the scorecard representation in the complementary-orbits scenario. Here, the comparison is between the three-satellite run “mc33” against the one-satellite baseline run “mc11” and the impact shown originates from the assimilation of both Metop-B and NOAA-19 microwave sounder radiances. Again, the strongest signals appear in the surface-based verification. Throughout the forecast range from 0 to 36 hours, there is a consistent and statistically significant positive impact in temperature, humidity-related variables, and cloud cover. The impact in cloud base height is positive and significant out to the 24-hour lead time. The impact in mean sea level pressure is positive and statistically significant at lead times from 9 to 36 hours, but not in the very short range.

Figure 3: Scorecard representation of the verification scores in the MetCoOp winter experiment for the three-satellite run in the complementary-orbits scenario. The interpretation is as in Figure 2.

The precipitation scores in Figure 3 are mixed and largely insignificant, and so are the scores of near-surface wind. Also the upper-air scores are for most parts insignificant, although on balance the weak signals tend to be more often positive than negative. Statistically significant impacts in the upper-air verification include the positive signals in specific (Q) and relative humidity (RH) at 850 hPa as well as in wind speed (S) at 300 hPa. Overall, the assimilation of new satellite data verifies more favourably in Figure 3 than in Figure 2.

3.2 Impact in individual model runs at winter

The scorecards presented above demonstrate a robust impact from the additional radiance data on certain variables in the surface-based verification. To quantify the impact, and also to evaluate how the impact builds up when the additional satellites are introduced one by one, it is useful to intercompare the verification scores of individual model runs. This is done in Figure 4 for selected variables including those where the scorecards show a particularly clear impact. Again, the verification metric is the forecast RMSE and it is shown relative to the one-satellite baseline run. Positive impact from the additional satellite data shows up as values higher than zero on the y-axis. The confidence intervals (bars) are at 95% level.

The positive impact from the additional satellite data is the clearest in the verification against observations of specific humidity at two metre height (the panel at top right in Figure 4). The black line (“mc21”) indicates that the first additional satellite in the single-orbit scenario reduces the forecast RMSE by almost 2% at very short range and by more than 1% at lead times up to 12 hours. The first and second additional satellites together (blue line, “mc31”) reduce the RMSE by 2-3% in the first few hours and by more than 1% at forecast lead times until 18 hours. In the complementary-orbits scenario the RMSE reductions are larger. Here, the first additional satellite (red line, “mc22”) shows an initial RMSE reduction of 3-4% and the reduction remains greater than 1% until the 24-hour lead time. The first and second additional satellites together (green lines, “mc33”) show an initial RMSE reduction of approximately 5%. On the basis of the verification against specific humidity alone, it is fair to conclude that

- the benefit from the additional satellites in the complementary-orbits scenario is twice as large as that in the single-orbit scenario, and that
- the additional benefit from bringing the second additional satellite in is half of the benefit from bringing the first additional satellite in.

Other verifying observables do not let us draw conclusions as firm as those discussed above. The verification against temperature at two metre height is qualitatively similar as the verification against specific humidity, but the strength of the signal is weaker and the 1% RMSE reduction is achieved only in the case of the three-satellite run in the complementary-orbits scenario and only at very short lead times. The behaviour is qualitatively similar also in the verification against cloud cover. In the case of mean sea level pressure, the new satellites appear more beneficial in the complementary-orbits scenario, but the three-satellite runs do not outperform the two-satellite runs in either scenario.

Figure 4: Verification scores in the MetCoOp winter experiment for (top left) temperature at two metres height, (top right) specific humidity at two metres height, (bottom left) cloud cover, and (bottom right) pressure reduced to mean sea level. The lines indicate the RMSE reduction as compared with the one-satellite baseline run, and positive values on the y-axis show a positive impact. The confidence intervals (bars) are at 95% statistical significance level. The single-orbit scenario is shown in black (two satellites) and blue (three satellites). The complementary-orbits scenario is shown in red (two satellites) and green (three satellites).

Selected scores from the verification against radiosonde observations at upper levels are shown in Figure 5. No firm conclusions can be drawn from these noisy scores and the overlapping confidence intervals of the model runs. The clearest indication of an impact is in the geopotential height at 300 hPa (panel at top left): the complementary-orbits scenario outperforms the single-orbit scenario, and the three-satellite run outperforms the two-satellite run. The magnitude of the forecast RMSE reduction is at most on the order of 0.5%. The other scores, including wind speed at 300 hPa (top right), temperature at 850 hPa (bottom left), and relative humidity at 850 hPa (bottom right), are only in broad terms consistent with the idea of greater impact in the complementary-orbits scenario.

Figure 5: Verification scores in the MetCoOp winter experiment for (top left) geopotential height at 300 hPa pressure, (top right) wind speed at 300 hPa, (bottom left) temperature at 850 hPa, and (bottom right) relative humidity at 850 hPa. The verification metrics, confidence intervals and line colours are as in Figure 4.

3.3 Verification in terms of observation-to-background data fit

In addition to the traditional verification of forecasts against surface and radiosonde observations, we consider the impact that the additional microwave sounder radiance data has on the quality of background field in the data assimilation. To do this, we compute statistics of Observation minus Background (OmB) departure for all assimilated data in each model run and produce figures of the control-normalised standard deviation in OmB for various observation types. The interpretation of these figures is such that where the control-normalised standard deviation is less than one, the assimilation of additional data has improved the quality of the short-range forecast (i.e., the background field). The standard deviation of OmB is then lower in the model run than in the one-satellite baseline run. Figure 6 shows the outcome for

temperature data collected by aircrafts, thermal radiance data collected from the Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI), and microwave radiance data from the MWHS-2 instrument.

In general, the data fits to independent observation types show very little impact in these model runs. This is true in particular when it comes to in situ -type measurements taken by radiosondes and aircrafts (see the example of aircraft-measured temperature data in the left-hand-side panel in Figure 6). Remotely-sensed data show somewhat more impact. The complementary-orbits scenario stands out in the verification against IASI radiance data (middle panel). There is an improvement of up to 7-8% in the data fit at channels sensitive to temperature in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. However, this impact is no greater in the three-satellite run (green line) than in the two-satellite run (red line). The single-orbit scenario shows practically no impact in the verification against IASI. The clearest indication of an impact is in the verification against MWHS-2 radiances (panel at right). This impact is qualitatively similar to what is seen in the verification against near-surface humidity. The impact is weaker in the single-orbit scenario than in the complementary-orbits scenario, and in both scenarios the three-satellite run outperforms the two-satellite run. The benefit of the satellite data is the most on MWHS-2 channels 13-14, that are broadly sensitive to tropospheric humidity in lower- to mid-troposphere.

Figure 6: Baseline-normalised standard deviation of Observation minus Background (OmB) departure in the MetCoOp winter experiment for aircraft-based temperature data (left), radiance data from the Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI) (middle), and MWHS-2 microwave radiance data (right). Values less than 1.0 on the x-axis indicate an improvement on top of the one-satellite baseline run. Confidence intervals (bars) are at 95% statistical significance level. Line colours are as in Figures 4 and 5.

3.4 Verification scores in the additional summer experiment

The headline forecast scores in the additional MetCoOp summer experiment are shown in Figure 7. Given the clean and robust positive impact seen in the winter experiment (see Figure 4), the impacts shown in Figure 7 are surprisingly small. The scores are almost exclusively not statistically significant and for most parts the impact is perfectly neutral. There are weak suggestions of a positive impact in near-surface temperature at the 3-12 hour lead times, but these are balanced out by equally weak suggestions of a negative impact at 15- to 24-hour lead times. Also in mean sea level pressure, there is a slight suggestion of a negative impact at short lead times. While the results obtained in this relatively short two-week evaluation period are inconclusive, it feels reasonable to assume a seasonal dependence in the way the MetCoOp NWP system responds to the introduction of additional satellite data. The impact appears considerably stronger in winter than in summer.

Figure 7: Headline verification scores in the MetCoOp summer experiment. The panels are laid out as in Figure 4 and the lines represent the three-satellite run in the complementary-orbits scenario.

4. Results in the AROME-Arctic operational domain

4.1 Scorecard-based overall impression of the impact at summer

Figure 8 is a scorecard representation of the forecast impact in the AROME-Arctic domain from introducing two additional satellites in the single-orbit scenario in the summer experiment. It is immediately obvious that the overall impact from the additional data is weaker in the AROME-Arctic summer run than in the equivalent run with the MetCoOp setup in winter (see Figure 2). There is a robust and statistically significant positive impact only in the verification against near-surface humidity (Td2m, Q2m, RH2m) and only out to the 12-hour forecast lead time. Beyond 12 hours, the impact remains mostly positive but without significance at 95% level. In terms of precipitation (AccPcp3h, AccPcp6h, AccPcp12h) and cloud-related (CCtot, Cbase) observations, the verification is somewhat more positive in the AROME-Arctic setup than at MetCoOp, but these scores are only occasionally significant. On the other hand, the scores against mean sea level pressure (Pmsl) are significantly negative throughout the full range of lead times, and the same is true at most lead times in the verification against near-surface temperature (T2m) and wind (D10m, S10m). In the verification against radiosonde observations, the scores of geopotential height and temperature are slightly positive but generally without significance. The scores on humidity and wind are, on balance, more negative than positive, but again without statistical significance. The scores at the zero-hour lead time are fairly consistently negative. This may be just an artefact of the verification method and the fact that the dominance of radiosonde observations in the data assimilation is by design the stronger the less there is satellite data assimilated in the model run. However, it is worth noting that the zero-hour lead time does not stand out as clearly in the verification of the MetCoOp experiment.

Figure 8: Scorecard representation of the verification scores in the AROME-Arctic summer experiment for the three-satellite run in the single-orbit scenario.

The verification scores for the three-satellite run in the complementary-orbits scenario are illustrated in the scorecard shown in Figure 9. Consistently with the results of the MetCoOp winter experiment (Section 3), this scenario of additional satellite data appears the more beneficial one. Robust and statistically significant impact in near-surface humidity variables extends out to the 24-hour forecast lead time. There are indications of a positive impact at short range also when verifying against two metre temperature observations. The scores against mean sea level pressure are negative out to the forecast lead time of 18 hours, but not beyond that. Near-surface wind, as well as both precipitation and cloud-related observations, indicate a neutral or marginally positive forecast impact from the satellite data. There are signs of a weak positive impact on the upper-air variables as revealed by the scores against geopotential height at 300 and 500 hPa pressure levels, as well as against temperature at 500 and 850 hPa levels. In contrast with the single-orbits scenario, the scores at the zero-hour lead time are mostly insignificant.

Figure 9: Scorecard representation of the verification scores in the AROME-Arctic summer experiment for the three-satellite run in the complementary-orbits scenario.

4.2 Impact in individual model runs at summer

The forecast scores computed against the selected surface-based observation types are shown for individual model runs in Figure 10. The forecast system performance improvement on top of the one-satellite baseline run is relatively small, especially in comparison with the results shown in Section 3 for the MetCoOp winter experiment. Again, the clearest and strongest impact is found in the verification against two-metre specific humidity. At most, that is in the three-satellite run of the complementary-orbits scenario, the reduction in forecast RMSE is approximately 1% at lead times up to 15 hours and 0.5% at the longer lead times. Also the two-satellite run indicates a positive, though slightly weaker, impact. The model runs in the scenario of a single orbital plane show no sign of a positive impact on near-surface humidity: in fact there is a weak negative forecast impact in the three-satellite run at short lead times.

Figure 10: As Figure 4, but for the AROME-Arctic summer experiment.

Apart from specific humidity, the near-surface variables show only few clear signals. Two-metre temperature and cloud cover are marginally on the positive side at most lead times, but the scores are insignificant and the different model runs verify on top of each other. Exceptionally, there is a negative forecast impact against mean sea level pressure in the complementary-orbits scenario at short lead times. Beyond the nine-hour lead time, these scores are neutral, while they are slightly on the positive side in the two runs of the single-orbit scenario.

The scores computed against selected upper-air variables are shown in Figure 11. Here, the power of verification is severely limited by the scarcity of radiosonde stations inside the AROME-Arctic domain: the scores are computed from four stations' data only (in comparison, there are 25-27 radiosonde stations in the verification at MetCoOp). Consequently, the confidence intervals are wide and statistically significant signals are sparse. It is noted though that the additional satellite data in the complementary-orbits scenario improves the geopotential forecast at 300 hPa, and this is significant at the 18-hour lead time. There is a positive impact also in the temperature verification at 850 hPa. The single-orbit scenario shows no significant impacts in the verification against radiosondes.

Figure 11: As Figure 5, but for the AROME-Arctic summer experiment.

4.3 Verification in terms of observation-to-background data fit

The short-range verification based on the OmB statistics in the AROME-Arctic summer experiment is shown for the selected observation types in Figure 12. Consistently with Figure 6, there is minimal impact on aircraft-measured temperature data (left panel). The runs of the complementary-orbits scenario show a notable improvement on the data fit to tropospheric-sensitive channels in IASI (middle panel). The improvement peaks at the 200-300 hPa level where it reaches 3% in both the two- and three-satellite runs. In the data fit to the humidity-sensitive channels of MWHS-2 (right panel), all model runs show significant improvements. In contrast to what is seen in the MetCoOp winter experiment, this impact is stronger in the single-orbit scenario than in the case of complementary orbits. At most the improvement in the data fit to MWHS-2 exceeds 5% in the three-satellite run of the single-orbit scenario.

Figure 12: As Figure 6, but for the AROME-Arctic summer experiment.

4.4 Verification scores in the additional winter experiment

Figure 13 shows the headline forecast scores in the additional AROME-Arctic winter experiment. Although there are not many statistically significant scores, there are suggestions of a positive impact at short range in several forecast parameters. There is an initial 1% improvement in the forecast RMSE in near-surface temperature, but this does not persist beyond the six-hour forecast lead time. In terms of near-surface specific humidity, the initial positive impact accounts for more than 2% improvement and persists out to the 12-hour lead time. The most robust positive impact appears in

the verification against cloud cover. Here, the RMSE improvement is close to 2% with statistical significance reached at most lead times out to 15 hours. The mean sea level pressure verifies neutrally though.

The impacts seen in Figure 13 at short lead times are at least twice as large as the corresponding signals in the three-satellite complementary-orbits run in the AROME-Arctic summer experiment. Given the relatively small sample of forecasts in this two-week evaluation period and the consequently wide confidence intervals, it is not possible to draw firm conclusions. However, there is an indication that the impact from satellite data in the AROME-Arctic setup is likely to be stronger in winter than in summer. This is consistent with results obtained in the MetCoOp setup.

Figure 13: Headline verification scores in the AROME-Arctic winter experiment. The panels are laid out as in Figure 10 and the lines represent the three-satellite run in the complementary-orbits scenario.

5. Discussion

As presented in Sections 3 and 4, the impact of the additional satellite data appears stronger in the verification against near-surface observations than in the verification against radiosondes. For instance, the surface-based verification in the MetCoOp domain shows RMSE reductions of up to 5% in specific humidity and cloud cover, while the RMSE reduction in the radiosonde-based verification of humidity in the lower troposphere is at best 2-4%. At least in part this discrepancy can be attributed to the number of available radiosonde data being insufficient to proper verification. Hypothetically, one would expect the RMSE reduction from any improvement in the update of observational input to be a smooth function of the forecast lead time, as long as the verification scheme is robust and there are sufficiently many independent verifying observations. However, figures presented in Sections 3 and 4 do not generally show such smooth behaviour. In the one particular case where the RMSE reduction over lead time is reasonably smooth, that is Figure 4, the verification is based on data collected from 600 – 1000 observing stations, most of them reporting hourly over the course of the full six-week evaluation time period. The number of radiosonde data in the verification is far less, because the radiosonde stations are more sparse and also their typical reporting frequency is twelve (not one or even three) hours. Consequently, the confidence intervals in the radiosonde-based verification are wide and the scores appear to jump erratically from one lead time to another.

The relative lack of impact against radiosonde observations may also in part be due to the treatment of data as point observations at the site of the station and at the time of the radiosonde launch. In reality, the measurements are taken along the trajectory of the balloon. Ignoring the time dimension and spatial dimensions (except for the vertical one) reduces representativeness of the observation and makes it harder to gain improvements in forecast scores, even if the numerical analysis and forecast benefit from genuine system improvements.

The impact from the additional satellites appears strongest in the surface-based verification of humidity-related variables and there is notably less benefit in the verification against temperature, mean sea level pressure, and wind. The relative weakness in the impact of temperature, pressure and wind is attributed to the large-scale mixing process that is applied as part of the limited-area NWP cycling. The process merges large-scale information from a global NWP model with the limited-area model's own short-range forecast field, and the merged output is used as the background field in the data assimilation. In HARMONIE-AROME systems, the large-scale mixing is applied to temperature, pressure and wind, but not to

humidity. This allows more freedom and potential for the humidity field to change during the data assimilation, thus leaving more room for the impact from the additional satellite data.

Both MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic experiments suggest more benefit from satellite data in winter than in summer. Unfortunately, given the short time coverage of the additional experiments, the conclusiveness of such seasonal dependence remains limited. Regardless, the seasonal dependence is the most likely explanation for the large differences seen in the forecast impact between the full six-week evaluation periods at winter in MetCoOp and at summer at AROME-Arctic. It is obvious that typical meteorological conditions at high Northern latitudes vary a lot over the course of a year. There are often considerable baroclinic activity (i.e., fronts) and low pressure systems dominating the weather in winter, while small-scale convective cells play only a minor role. In summer, the convective events are much more common and the influence of baroclinic activity in synoptic scales is relatively little. A possible interpretation is that the data assimilation in HARMONIE-AROME is more effective in synoptic than in convective scales, even if the grid resolution and the NWP system's dynamical core are designed to allow for some explicit description of convection too. Moreover, there is an alternative (or complementary) interpretation that the existing network of verifying surface and radiosonde stations is not capable of capturing genuine forecasting system improvements in convective scale. Either of these interpretations would be consistent with the observed seasonal variability in the NWP systems' response to satellite data.

Since room for speculation remains, the known system differences between MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic are worth bringing up for discussion. These include at least the following aspects:

- Background error statistics are specified differently. Specifically, the standard deviation of assumed background error is in the order of 50-70% larger in AROME-Arctic than in MetCoOp. There are no differences in the specification of observation errors, so observations are given relatively more weight at AROME-Arctic. However, it remains unclear whether this difference has any implications on the extraction of meteorological information from satellite data.
- The diurnal evolution of the satellite data availability and usage are surprisingly different in the two systems. At MetCoOp, the daily dose of each polar orbiter data consists of descending node overpasses at two consecutive analysis times and of ascending node overpasses at another two consecutive analysis times. In between the descending and ascending nodes, there is one analysis time that sees no data. The AROME-Arctic domain is further North and sees many more overpasses, so that data from a given satellite may be used at up to five consecutive analysis times. Consequently, relatively little

benefit is expected from the third orbital plane: even with two planes only there is usually satellite data available at all analysis times. This aspect is illustrated in Table 3.

- It is also important to remember that the AROME-Arctic domain suffers from a relatively poor coverage of synoptic and radiosonde observing stations, and consequently the verification scores are less reliable than at MetCoOp. The locations of the verifying surface stations inside the modelling domains are shown in Figure 14.

Table 3: Number of satellites that provide microwave sounding capability at each analysis time in each of the conducted model runs. Each shading colour represents either 0, 1, 2, or 3 satellites.

	00 UTC	03 UTC	06 UTC	09 UTC	12 UTC	15 UTC	18 UTC	21 UTC
mc31	3	3	0	3	3	0	0	0
mc21	2	2	0	2	2	0	0	0
mc11	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
mc22	1	1	0	2	2	0	1	1
mc33	1	1	1	3	2	1	2	1
aa31	3	3	3	3	3	0	0	0
aa21	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0
aa11	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
aa22	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1
aa33	1	2	1	3	3	1	1	1

Figure 14: Locations of verifying surface stations inside the MetCoOp (left) and AROME-Arctic (right) limited-area model domains. The colouring of the dots is irrelevant in this context.

There is a fair chance that the present study underestimates the impact that microwave radiance data will have in the next decade. Apart from the use of 4D-Var instead of 3D-Var in the analysis of upper-air variables, this impact evaluation relies on data assimilation systems similar to the currently operational setups in the Nordic countries. As it stands, tropospheric-sensitive radiance data are assimilated only in clear-sky conditions. There is a considerable ongoing effort being directed to the development of the assimilation of cloud-affected radiances too. Given that the assimilation of such cloud-affected data (via the so-called all-sky route) is mature in global NWP systems (Geer et al., 2017), the method can realistically be expected to reach operational status at the Nordic NWP systems in the next 3-5 years' time. The development will result in a considerable increase in the number of assimilated data, and the extraction of meteorological data will consequently become more advanced and effective than what it is now.

Finally, one may ask how this study answers the question of the expected EPS-Sterna constellation impact. The conducted experiments suggest that the constellation will provide a boost in the limited-area forecasting of near-surface temperature, humidity and cloud cover. The impact will be the greatest in the forecast of humidity and cloud at forecast lead times up to 24 hours and it can be expected to be greater in winter than in summer. However, it is not straightforward to extrapolate from the quantitative impact as demonstrated in Sections 3 and 4 to the foreseen constellation impact. A very crude quantified estimate can be derived from the following set of assumptions:

1. *The one-satellite baseline setup* used in this study is sufficiently representative of a *state-of-the-art limited-area NWP system setup* at the time when the EPS-Sterna constellation becomes operational.
2. The EPS-Sterna constellation will consist of *six satellites placed in two complementary orbital planes* with three satellites in each plane.
3. The impact demonstrated in the MetCoOp winter experiment (Section 3) for the scenario of *two additional satellites in complementary orbits* is representative of the hypothetical impact from a combination of *two AWS satellites operated in complementary orbital planes*.
4. As suggested by the results shown in Section 3, *doubling the number of satellites* will enhance the constellation impact by *50%*.
5. Another *50% increase in the number of satellites* will enhance the constellation impact by *another 25%*.

These assumptions imply that the impact of the future EPS-Sterna constellation will be approximately $1.25 \times 1.5 = 1.875$ times larger than the impact quantified in Sections 3 and 4 for the three-satellite, complementary-orbits, run against the one-satellite baseline. In winter, since there is approximately 5% reduction in the forecast RMSE in near-surface specific humidity at short lead times, we could expect up to 9% RMSE reduction from the complete operational EPS-Sterna constellation in this forecast variable. In absolute terms, short-range forecast RMSE of 0.30 g/kg would be reduced to 0.273 g/kg. In this calculation, the impact expectation in summer is less than 2% of RMSE reduction, equivalent to reducing from 0.70 g/kg to 0.68 g/kg. In practice, the impact will probably be somewhat weaker, because the assumptions listed above are likely not perfectly valid. In particular, the one-satellite baseline system used in this study is by design a depleted version of operational NWP system setups. Therefore, the 1.875 scaling factor presented here should only be considered as a reasonable upper bound of the expected constellation impact.

6. Conclusions

This study presents an evaluation of the meteorological impact obtained from assimilating microwave sounder radiance data into limited-area NWP systems at high Northern latitudes. The evaluation is based on numerical experiments conducted using state-of-the-art NWP systems similar to the currently operational setups at MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic groups. As a notable exception from the operational settings, the numerical analysis of upper-air variables is based on the advanced 4D-Var data assimilation method, in contrast with the 3D-Var method that

remains the operational choice for now. Verification of the conducted model runs indicate a substantial positive impact from the satellite data.

Bringing additional satellite data on top of a one-satellite baseline run produces measurable benefits in the forecast of temperature, humidity, and cloud cover. The most uncontroversial signals are seen in the verification against observations taken at synoptic surface stations. The beneficial impact is particularly clear in the forecast of specific humidity in the MetCoOp domain in winter. At most, the associated reduction in forecast RMSE is approximately 5%. However, the verification of upper-air meteorological fields against radiosonde-based observations shows only marginal benefits from the additional satellite data. The conducted experiments in the MetCoOp domain in summer time indicate far less beneficial impacts. A similar seasonal dependency is observed in the experiments conducted in the more Northerly AROME-Arctic domain.

There is a realistic chance that the future impact from microwave radiance data is greater than the impact presented in this work. This expectation follows from the considerable effort taken at the European limited-area modelling consortia towards assimilating the data through the so-called all-sky route, thus enabling efficient extraction of information not only in cloud-free situations but in cloud-dominated scenes too.

Particularly at MetCoOp domain, the model runs indicate that it is more beneficial to introduce new satellites into orbital planes complementary to each other (the complementary-orbits scenario) than to enhance the observing system in a single orbital plane only (the single-orbit scenario). Broadly speaking, the impact of the additional satellites in the former scenario is twice as much as in the latter scenario. In either scenario, the additional benefit from bringing the second additional satellite in is half of the benefit from bringing the first additional satellite in.

It remains somewhat speculative as regards to how the beneficial impact of satellite data will scale up in the future EPS-Sterna constellation. According to the results presented here, it is realistic to expect a constellation impact that accounts for a reduction in excess of 5% on short-range forecast RMSE of near-surface humidity and cloud cover. In winter conditions, this would correspond to reducing the forecast RMSE of specific humidity from 0.30 g/kg to 0.28 g/kg. In near-surface temperature, the forecast RMSE reduction will be in the order of 1-2% only, that is e.g. from 2.00 K to 1.97 K.

References

- Auligne, T., A. P. McNally, D. P. Dee, 2007: Adaptive bias correction for satellite data in a numerical weather prediction system. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **133**, 631-642, DOI:10.1002/qj.56.
- Benacek, P. and M. Mile, 2019: Satellite Bias Correction in the Regional Model ALADIN/CZ: Comparison of Different VarBC approaches. *Monthly Weather Review*, **147**, 3223-3239, DOI:10.1175/MWR-D-18-0359.1.
- Bengtsson, L., U. Andrae, T. Aspelien, Y. Batrak, J. Calvo, W. de Rooy, E. Gleeson, B. Hansen-Sass, M. Homleid, M. Hortal, K.-I. Ivarsson, G. Lenderink, S. Niemelä, K. P. Nielsen, J. Onvlee, L. Rontu, P. Samuelsson, D. S. Muñoz, A. Subias, S. Tijm, V. Toll, X. Yang, and M. Køltzow, 2017: The HARMONIE-AROME Model Configuration in the ALADIN-HIRLAM NWP System. *Monthly Weather Review*, **145**, 1919-1935, DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-16-0417.1.
- Courtier, P., J.-N. Thepaut, A. Hollingsworth, 1994: A strategy for operational implementation of 4D-Var using an incremental approach. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **120**, 1367-1388.
- Geer, A., F. Baordo, N. Bormann, P. Chambon, S. English, M. Kazumori, H. Lawrence, P. Lean, K. Lonitz, C. Lupu, 2017: The growing impact of satellite observations sensitive to humidity, cloud and precipitation. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **143**, 3189-3206, DOI:10.1002/qj.3172.
- Gustafsson, N., X.-Y. Huang, X. Yang, K. Mogensen, M. Lindskog, O. Vignes, T. Wilhelmsson, S. Thorsteinsson, 2012: Four-dimensional variational data assimilation for a limited area model. *Tellus A*, **64**, 14985, DOI:10.3402/tellusa.v64i0.14985.
- Müller, M., M. Homleid, K.-I. Ivarsson, M. Køltzow, M. Lindskog, K. H. Midtbø, U. Andrae, T. Aspelien, L. Berggren, D. Bjørge, P. Dahlgren, J. Kristiansen, R. Randriamampianina, M. Ridal, and O. Vignes, 2017: AROME-MetCoOp: A Nordic Convective-Scale Operational Weather Prediction Model. *Weather and Forecasting*, **32**, 609-627, DOI: 10.1175/WAF-D-16-0099.1.
- Randriamampianina, R., H. Schyberg, and M. Mile, 2019: Observing System Experiments with an Arctic Mesoscale Numerical Weather Prediction Model. *Remote Sensing*, **11**, 981, DOI: 10.3390/rs11080981.